

Appendix A - Complete search strategies to ensure reproducibility

This appendix provides the complete, unabridged search strategies used for the literature review, as described in **Section 2.1** of the main manuscript.

To ensure full transparency and reproducibility, the exact search strings, Boolean operators, and filters applied to each database - PubMed, Scopus, and SciELO - are presented in the tables below. The strategies include comprehensive keywords in both English and Portuguese to provide a robust and replicable overview of the literature on the topic.

Table A1 - PubMed search strategy.

	Search strings	Results
#1	Search: (((leptospira[MeSH Terms]) OR (leptospirosis[MeSH Terms])) OR (leptospira[Title/Abstract])) OR (leptospirosis[Title/Abstract]) "leptospira"[MeSH Terms] OR "leptospirosis"[MeSH Terms] OR "leptospira"[Title/Abstract] OR "leptospirosis"[Title/Abstract] Translations leptospira[MeSH Terms]: "leptospira"[MeSH Terms] leptospirosis[MeSH Terms]: "leptospirosis"[MeSH Terms]	14,619
#2	Search: (((((((rain[MeSH Terms]) OR (floods[MeSH Terms])) OR (cyclonic storm[MeSH Terms])) OR (rain[Title/Abstract])) OR (rainfall[Title/Abstract])) OR (floods[Title/Abstract])) OR (flooding[Title/Abstract])) OR (cyclone[Title/Abstract])) OR (typhoon[Title/Abstract])) OR (inundation[Title/Abstract])) OR (precipitation[Title/Abstract])) OR (hurricane[Title/Abstract])	154,803

	<p>"rain"[MeSH Terms] OR "floods"[MeSH Terms] OR "cyclonic storms"[MeSH Terms] OR "rain"[Title/Abstract] OR "rainfall"[Title/Abstract] OR "floods"[Title/Abstract] OR "flooding"[Title/Abstract] OR "cyclone"[Title/Abstract] OR "typhoon"[Title/Abstract] OR "inundation"[Title/Abstract] OR "precipitation"[Title/Abstract] OR "hurricane"[Title/Abstract]</p> <p>Translations</p> <p>rain[MeSH Terms]: "rain"[MeSH Terms]</p> <p>floods[MeSH Terms]: "floods"[MeSH Terms]</p> <p>cyclonic storm[MeSH Terms]: "cyclonic storms"[MeSH Terms]</p>	
<p>#1 AND #2</p>	<p>Search: (#1) AND (#2) Filters: Free full text, Adaptive Clinical Trial, Case Reports, Classical Article, Clinical Study, Clinical Trial, Clinical Trial, Phase I, Clinical Trial, Phase II, Clinical Trial, Phase III, Clinical Trial, Phase IV, Clinical Trial Protocol, Comparative Study, Controlled Clinical Trial, Equivalence Trial, Evaluation Study, Historical Article, Multicenter Study, Observational Study, Overall, Pragmatic Clinical Trial, Randomized Controlled Trial, Randomized Controlled Trial, Veterinary, Research Support, American Recovery and Reinvestment Act, Research Support, N.I.H., Extramural, Research Support, N.I.H., Intramural, Research Support, Non-U.S. Gov't, Research Support, U.S. Gov't, Research Support, U.S. Gov't, Non-P.H.S., Research Support, U.S. Gov't, P.H.S., Validation Study, Clinical Trial, Veterinary, Observational Study, Veterinary, from 2014 - 2024</p> <p>((("leptospira"[MeSH Terms] OR "leptospirosis"[MeSH Terms] OR "leptospira"[Title/Abstract] OR "leptospirosis"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("rain"[MeSH Terms] OR "floods"[MeSH Terms] OR "cyclonic storms"[MeSH Terms] OR "rain"[Title/Abstract] OR "rainfall"[Title/Abstract] OR "floods"[Title/Abstract] OR "flooding"[Title/Abstract] OR "cyclone"[Title/Abstract] OR "typhoon"[Title/Abstract] OR "inundation"[Title/Abstract] OR "precipitation"[Title/Abstract] OR "hurricane"[Title/Abstract])) AND ((frft[Filter]) AND (adaptiveclinicaltrial[Filter] OR casereports[Filter] OR classicalarticle[Filter] OR clinicalstudy[Filter] OR clinicaltrial[Filter] OR clinicaltrialphasei[Filter] OR clinicaltrialphaseii[Filter] OR clinicaltrialphaseiii[Filter] OR clinicaltrialphaseiv[Filter] OR clinicaltrialprotocol[Filter] OR comparativestudy[Filter] OR controlledclinicaltrial[Filter] OR equivalencetrial[Filter] OR evaluationstudy[Filter] OR historicalarticle[Filter] OR multicenterstudy[Filter] OR observationalstudy[Filter])</p>	<p>80</p>

	<p>OR overall[Filter] OR pragmaticclinicaltrial[Filter] OR randomizedcontrolledtrial[Filter] OR randomizedcontrolledtrialveterinary[Filter] OR researchsupportamericanrecoveryandreinvestmentact[Filter] OR researchsupportnihextramural[Filter] OR researchsupportnihintramural[Filter] OR researchsupportnonusgovt[Filter] OR researchsupportusgovernment[Filter] OR researchsupportusgovtnonphs[Filter] OR researchsupportusgovtphs[Filter] OR validationstudy[Filter] OR veterinaryclinicaltrial[Filter] OR veterinaryobservationalstudy[Filter]) AND (2014:2024[pdat]))</p> <p>Translations</p> <p>leptospira[MeSH Terms]: "leptospira"[MeSH Terms]</p> <p>leptospirosis[MeSH Terms]: "leptospirosis"[MeSH Terms]</p> <p>rain[MeSH Terms]: "rain"[MeSH Terms]</p> <p>floods[MeSH Terms]: "floods"[MeSH Terms]</p> <p>cyclonic storm[MeSH Terms]: "cyclonic storms"[MeSH Terms]</p>	
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Table A2 - Scopus search strategy.

Search strings	Results
(TITLE-ABS-KEY (leptospirosis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (leptospira) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (flood) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (flooding) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (rainfall) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (rain) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (precipitation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (inundation) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (typhoon) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (cyclone) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (hurricane)) AND PUBYEAR > 2013 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))	365

Table A3 - SciELO search strategy.

Search strings	Results
<p>All index (Leptospira) OR (Leptospirosis) AND (Flood) OR (flooding) OR (rainfall) OR (rain) OR (precipitation) OR (inundation) OR (typhoon) OR (cyclone) OR (hurricane)</p> <p>Filters: Idioma: English Year: 2014-2024 Literature: Article</p>	70
<p>All index (Leptospira) OR (Leptospirose) AND (Enchente) OR (Inundação) OR (Chuva) OR (Tempestade) OR (Precipitação) OR (Ciclone) OR (Furacão) OR (Tufão)</p> <p>Filters: Idioma: Portuguese Year: 2014-2024 Literature: Article</p>	50